

Production of biogas from Napier grass, Banana peel and Cow dung

Kowrin Kishor Roy¹, Paban Barua Nishan², Dr. Sajal Chandra Banik³

^{1,2} Bsc. in ME, Chittagong University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh

³Professor, Department of ME, Chittagong University of Engineering and Technology, Bangladesh

kowrinkishor@gmail.com, pbnishan573@gmail.com*, baniksajal@cuet.ac.bd

Objectives:

1. To assess the biodegradability and biogas production potential of Napier grass, banana peels, and cow dung through anaerobic co-digestion.
2. To determine the methane yield, gas purity, and overall volume of biogas produced from these feedstocks.
3. To evaluate the economic feasibility and environmental impact of biogas generation using these locally available substrates.

Materials and Methods:

Napier grass, banana peels, and cow dung were prepared by cleaning, cutting, and mixing in three different proportions (1:1, 2:1, and 1:2). Fresh cow dung was used as the microbial inoculum. Anaerobic co-digestion was carried out in sealed 5 L HDPE digesters maintained at 30–35 °C for 23 days. Biogas output was recorded using the water displacement technique, while methane concentration and slurry pH were periodically measured to assess digestion performance.

Results:

Anaerobic co-digestion of cow dung, Napier grass, and banana peels produced varying biogas yields across three substrate ratios. The 1:1 mixture generated the highest cumulative gas volume of approximately 2,481 mL over 23 days, followed by the 2:1 and 1:2 mixtures with 2,045 mL and 1,615 mL, respectively. Peak daily gas production reached 250 mL around Day 15, indicating optimal methanogenic activity between Days 10–20. Gas composition analysis showed methane concentrations ranging from 20.25% to 23.29%, lower than the typical 60–70% for standard biogas. Oxygen intrusion was detected at 13–17%, suggesting incomplete sealing of the digesters. Hydrogen sulfide remained low (6–7 ppm), minimizing purification needs. Overall, the 1:1 ratio demonstrated superior gas yield, while operational improvements—particularly enhanced sealing and pH control—are necessary to increase methane content and energy potential.

Conclusion(s):

The study found that co-digesting cow dung with Napier grass and banana peel is feasible for biogas production. The highest yield (2,481 ml) was achieved using a 1:1 ratio of Napier grass to banana peel over 23 days. However, methane content was low (20–23%), likely due to oxygen intrusion. Improving digester sealing and pH stability could enhance gas quality. The process is economically practical and environmentally beneficial, as it utilizes low-cost agricultural residues while reducing organic waste. The approach offers a sustainable energy option using locally available organic waste.

Keywords: Biogas, Anaerobic digestion, Napier grass, Banana peel, Cow dung, Methane yield.

Figure:

Figure: Total gas production (ml) vs Day.

Sessions:

Engineering and Technology.